

Leaf scald disease of rice in Manipur, India

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Leaf scald disease of rice first occurred on 10–15 acres in Manipur (at the State Seed Multiplication Farm, Mantripukhri, Imphal) during 1973–74. Since then the disease has occurred widely in the state's major rice belt. In 1976–77, the disease was found infecting China 1039 in the State Rice Research Station, Wangbal. Recently a number of local and newly introduced high yielding varieties (see table) were infected by the disease. Ratna appears to have some resistance to the disease.

Although leaf scald is not as

Occurrence of rice leaf scald in Manipur, India.

Variety	Location	Reaction to the disease ^a	Remarks
Moirangphou	Thoubal, Bishenpur, and Imphal West I	S	A popular local variety
Cheena No. 1	Imphal West II	HS	A nondescript local cultivar gaining popularity
IET 1991	Imphal West I	S	First recorded on this variety and Jaya, 1973–74
China 988	Whole central valley	S	Popular variety introduced recently
China 1039	- do -	S	- do -
Jaya	- do -	S	This high yielding variety is extremely popular and widely cultivated
Ratna	- do -	MR	- do -
IR24	- do -	S	- do -

^aS = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible, MR = moderately resistant.

threatening as blast, its importance in Manipur is increasing because of the

changes in agrotechniques adopted in the state.

Phenol content: a possible biochemical parameter for resistance and susceptibility of the rice plant to *Helminthosporium oryzae*

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Brown spot disease of rice caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* appears as brownish to greyish oval-shaped lesions on the coleoptile, leaf lamina, leaf sheath, and glume, but rarely on the stem of the rice plant. Establishment of the disease depends on the compatibility between the host and the pathogen.

The parameter used to measure the resistance and susceptibility of the rice plant to brown spot is the number of lesions as well as their size. The present investigation indicates that phenol content of rice leaves could serve as the biochemical parameter.

Different varieties of rice were screened for resistance and susceptibility to *H. oryzae* in the field with the conventional method. The varieties were classified as resistant (R), moderately resistant (MR), and susceptible (S).

Twenty-four varieties (8 resistant, 8 moderately resistant, and 8 susceptible) were selected and the total phenol content of the healthy leaves was determined colorimetrically. A strong correlation existed between phenol content of rice leaves and susceptibility of the host to pathogenic attack; phenol content was highest in the resistant variety.

An artificially inoculated susceptible variety, pretreated with catechol (a phenolic compound), showed resistance to *H. oryzae*. Potato-dextrose agar,

supplemented with different concentrations of catechol, inhibited pathogen growth. The catechol concentration in the medium and the inhibitory growth of the pathogen were correlated. The results indicate that the phenol content of rice leaves acts as a possible biochemical parameter for disease resistance and susceptibility of the rice plant to *H. oryzae*.

Sugar, amino acids, protein, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and manganese contents were also analyzed, but varietal differences were not significant.

Reaction of some rices to bacterial blight, blast, and *Helminthosporium* leaf spot under field conditions

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One hundred and ninety rice selections and four standard cultivars — Jaya, PR106, Palman 579, and Basmati 370 — were sown in a randomized block at the Regional Rice Research Station,

Kapurthala, and at the Regional Research Station, Gurdaspur, of Punjab Agricultural University. Their reactions to bacterial blight were recorded in September 1977. Observations on blast and *Helminthosporium* leaf spot were recorded only at Gurdaspur, where conditions are ideal for their development.

Bacterial blight incidence was higher in all the cultures at Gurdaspur than at Kapurthala because environmental conditions there were more favorable (see table). The cross combinations Basmati 370/IR8, Basmati 370/IR480-5,